

Writing Proficiency Assessment in Language Teaching and Testing: A Case Study of English Departments at Universities in Islamabad

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Abstract

Language assessment refers to the process of evaluating an individual's language proficiency, skills, and abilities. This assessment can encompass various aspects of language, including speaking, listening, reading, writing, and comprehension. This research is a case study of language testing, where among the four of language skills, this study focuses on writing skill of the learners, to evaluate linguistic competence and abilities at beginner level. Moreover, the research adopts the framework of task-based language learning by Willis Jane (1996) to profoundly examine the phenomenon under exploration. The research design opted for this case study is the qualitative approach. Writing skills have been assessed via essay writing prompts of five students which is the sample for this study. The findings suggest that writing proficiency is a key issue for standardized assessment criteria. It further suggests that the examination of key criteria of essay such as thesis statement, organization, development of ideas, evidence and support, analysis, and language proficiency accentuates the multi-layered nature of writing evaluation. The conclusion also suggests that assessment in writing skills for language testing will help to develop critical thinking, accurate function of language, and ability to practice language, at beginner level. It becomes imperative to strike a balance between standardized evaluation and the recognition of individual linguistic styles and cultural influences as well. Furthermore, the research has emphasized the need for clear guidelines, consistency, and transparency in the assessment process in the department. Teachers and language professionals should collaborate to develop assessment tools that align with learning objectives and provide constructive feedback to aid learners in their linguistic development.

Keywords: Assessment, English language teaching, English essay, Writing skill, Task based approach.

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